

ASSESSING THE IMPACT OF SOWING WINDOWS ON RABI SORGHUM (*Sorghum bicolor* L.) VARIETIES¹Ashwini D. Thengane*, ²Godavari S. Gaikwad, ³P. S. Kamble, ⁴G.V. Thakre,¹ Post Graduate Scholar, Department of Agronomy, PGI, Dr. P.D.K.V., Akola (MS), India,² Assistant Professor, Department of Agronomy, Dr. P.D.K.V., Akola, (MS), India.³Sorghum Physiologist, Sorghum Research Unit, Dr. P.D.K.V., Akola (MS), India.⁴ Sorghum Agronomist, Sorghum Research Unit, Dr. P.D.K.V., Akola (MS), India.

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Abstract

The study investigated the assessing the impact of sowing windows on rabi sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* L.) varieties conducted during the year rabi 2023-24 at Sorghum Research Unit, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola. There were sixteen treatment combinations including four dates of sowing viz., D₁-14th October (42 MW), D₂- 21st October (42 MW), D₃- 28th October (43 MW) and D₄- 4th November (44 MW) and four varieties viz., V₁- M 35-1, V₂- Phule Suchitra, V₃- CSV-29R, and V₄- BJV-44 all replicated thrice in a Factorial Randomized Block Design (FRBD). Among the treatments, morpho-physiological traits viz., plant height, number of functional leaves, dry matter accumulation, days to 50% flowering, days to physiological maturity were significantly influenced due to different dates of sowing in sorghum. Maximum values of all these traits were recorded by sowing in D₁-14th October (42 MW) while out of four varieties V₄- BJV-44 was superior in respect morpho-physiological traits and yield.

Keywords: Sorghum, Sowing window, Varieties, morpho-physiological traits, yield.

Introduction:

Sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* L.) is the fifth most important food crop of the world after wheat, maize, rice and barley. Sorghum commonly known as great millet is an excellent source of riboflavin, vitamin B6, thiamine and minerals such as iron, potassium, manganese and magnesium and is an alternative grain to wheat for people with gluten intolerance. Sorghum is a highly reliable crop that grows well in hot and dry environments. It is "climate change ready crop". Sorghum is well known for drought tolerance. It is known as "Camel crop" and can withstand drought for long time.

India is the second largest producer of sorghum in the world, it occupies an area of 5.6 m ha with a production of 4.5 mt and productivity of 812 kg/ha (www.indiastat.com). Maharashtra ranks first in area and production and it occupies an area of 26.797 lakh ha with a production 14.275 lakh tonnes and productivity of 782 kg/ha. In Vidarbha region the area, production and productivity of rabi sorghum is 0.261 lakh ha, 0.259 lakh tonnes, 951 kg/ha. respectively.(www.mah.gov.in).

Sorghum Crop is exposed to a variety of weather conditions during its different phenophases of growth resulting in larger variations with regard to growth rate and yield. Rabi sorghum is grown from October to February. The best time of sowing for rabi sorghum is 15th October to reduce incidence of shoot fly, while irrigated sorghum can be sown up to the end of October. Early sown rabi sorghum is prone to heavy shoot fly incidence. Sowing time has an impact on sorghum growth stages. Number of days between sowing and flowering decreases as planting was delayed due to slower emergence and less rapid accumulation of heat units. Planting date affects not only the time from sowing to flowering but time from flowering to physiological maturity of grain sorghum.

The variation in planting dates modifies the microclimate to which the plants are exposed with an influence on biomass production and ultimately the yield. Therefore, it is necessary to acquire the knowledge of plant and environment interactions for enhancing yield. Climate change prediction of increase in temperature and decrease in rainfall and low humidity during flowering damage the flowers as well as foliage, desiccation of pollen and interfere with the pollination

Treatment Details:

Factor - A : Sowing windows	
D ₁	41 MW (7 – 14 Oct)
D ₂	42 MW (15 - 21 Oct)
D ₃	43 MW (22 - 28 Oct)
D ₄	44 MW (29 Oct – 4 Nov)
Factor – B : Varieties	

resulting in poor grain formation.

Sorghum is a warm-season, annual crop, favoured by high day and night temperatures and growth and yield of a crop. Sowing of the crop at right time ensures better plant growth and also inhibits weed growth. There are evidences that optimum time of sowing is one of the several cultural manipulations and play vital role in boosting up the yield, particularly in Indian sub continent where the optimum time of sowing varies to great extent due to varying agro-climatic conditions.

Optimum time of sowing for realizing maximum productivity of sorghum is decided by both climatic factors and management practices. Hence, there is an urgent need to understand the sorghum crop response to its different varieties combined with cultural practices such as sowing dates during rabi season in Maharashtra.

Materials and methods

The field experiment was conducted at Sorghum Research Unit, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola, Maharashtra, India during the Rabi season of 2023-24 (22^o 42' N latitude, 72^o 02' E longitude and at an altitude of 307.42 m above MSL).The gross plot size was 4.5 m x 3.00 m and net plot size was 3.6 m x 2.40 m. The experiment was laid out in Factorial Randomized Block Design (FRBD) with 16 treatments combinations comprising of 4 dates of sowing viz., D₁-14th October (41MW), D₂-21st October (42MW), D₃-28th (43 MW) and D₄- 4th November (43 MW) and four varieties viz., V₁- M 35-1, V₂- Phule Suchitra, V₃- CSV-29R, V₄- BJV-44 replicated three times. The soil of experimental field was Inceptisol, almost neutral in reaction (pH 7.68), low in organic carbon (0.53%), nitrogen (212.0 kg ha⁻¹) medium in available phosphorus (16.75 kg ha⁻¹) and medium in available potassium (363.00 kg ha⁻¹). Sowing was done with spacing of 45 cm x 15 cm (Row to Plant). Recommended basal dose of nitrogen (80 kg N ha⁻¹), phosphorus (40 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹) and potassium (40 K₂O kg ha⁻¹) was applied through urea, di-ammonium phosphate and muriate of potash. Meteorological data viz, rainfall, relative humidity, maximum and minimum temperature, bright sunshine hrs and day length were recorded from Agro-meteorological observatory of Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola, Maharashtra, India.

V ₁	M 35-1
V ₂	Phule Suchitra
V ₃	CSV-29R
V ₄	BJV-44

Results and Discussion:

Effect of different sowing dates and varieties on morpho-physiological traits, grain yield, biological yield and harvest index

Plant height (cm)

Plant height was significantly influenced by dates of sowing. The significantly higher plant height was recorded with the crop sown on 21st October (42 MW) and it was found at par with 14th October (41MW) at harvest, whereas 4th November (44 MW) recorded least plant height at harvest. Among the varieties BJV-44 recorded significantly highest mean plant height. The lowest plant height was recorded with variety M-35-1. Similar results were reported by (Bhavya 2015). An interaction effect was found to be non-significant in respect of plant height.

Number of functional leaves

In case of number of functional leaves was found to be non significant both sowing windows and varieties and their interaction.

Dry matter weight (g plant⁻¹)

During crop growing period, increase in dry matter weight was continuous up to at harvest stage. The rate of increase was slow up to 90 days stage. Thereafter, it accelerated most between 90 and at harvest stage. Different dates of sowing have significant influenced on dry matter accumulation plant⁻¹. Sowing in 21st October (42 MW) (217.08 g) accumulated higher dry matter weight plant⁻¹ and it was found at par with 14th October (41MW). Sowing in 4th November (44 MW) recorded the lower dry matter accumulation (198.78 g) Similar findings were reported by (Kalhapure and Shete 2013). Higher dry matter accumulation plant⁻¹ (213.38 g) at harvest was recorded with variety M-35-1 which was significantly higher rest of all varieties.

Days to 50% flowering (DAS)

Sowing at 14th October (41MW) (81.17 DAS) recorded significantly higher number of days to 50% flowering and at par with crop sown on 21st October (42 MW) (79.67 DAS). Least no. of days to 50 % flowering was recorded with crop sown on 4th November (44 MW) Differences due to varieties were significant. No. of days to 50% flowering among varieties may mainly be attributed to their genetic potential rather than the effect of external weather parameters which similar range along the growing period of varieties. Among the varieties significantly higher no. of days to 50% flowering recorded with BJV-44 which was at par with Phule Suchitra. Lowest no. of days to 50% flowering was recorded with M-35-1. Interaction effect of sowing windows and *rabi* sorghum varieties was found to be non significant. Similar findings were reported by (Frank 2011)

Days to physiological maturity (DAS)

Sowing at 21st October (42 MW) (124.25 DAS) recorded significantly higher number of days to physiological maturity and at par with 14th October (41MW) (124.08 DAS). The lowest no. of days to physiological maturity was recorded with the crop sown on 4th November (44 MW) (119.08 DAS). Similar findings were reported by Desai et al. (2015). Differences due to varieties were significant. No. of days to physiological maturity among varieties may mainly be attributed to their genetic potential rather than the effect of external weather parameters which similar range along the growing period of varieties. Among the varieties significantly highest no. of days to physiological maturity with BJV-44. Lowest no. of days to physiological maturity was recorded with M-35-1. Interaction effect of sowing windows and *rabi* sorghum varieties was found to be non significant.

Grain yield (kg ha⁻¹)

Among the sowing dates, significantly higher mean grain yield (2583 kg ha⁻¹) was observed with crop sown on 21st October (42 MW) and it was found at par with crop sown on 14th October (41 MW). Lowest grain yield (2101 kg ha⁻¹) was recorded with crop sown on 4th November (44 MW). The grain yield was found to decrease with the delay in sowing dates and significantly lowest mean grain yield was recorded under 4th November (44 MW) sowing condition. Similar results were reported by (Pawar *et al.* 2004). Among the varieties also recorded significant differences for grain yield and the genotype BJV-44 recorded significantly highest mean grain yield (2753 kg ha⁻¹) which was followed by the variety Phule Suchitra (2484 kg ha⁻¹). However the lower mean grain yield (1924 kg ha⁻¹) was recorded by the variety M-35-1 and followed by CSV-29R (2259 kg ha⁻¹). Similar study were reported by (Shravanakumar *et al.* 2015) Grain yield (kg ha⁻¹) was not influenced significantly due to interaction effect of sowing windows and *rabi* sorghum variety.

Biological yield (kg ha⁻¹)

Among the sowing dates, significantly higher mean biological yield (10641 kg ha⁻¹) was observed with crop sown on 21st October (42 MW) and it was found at par with 14th October (41MW). Lowest biological yield (9001 kg ha⁻¹) was recorded with crop sown on 4th November (44 MW). The biological yield was found to decrease with the delay in sowing dates. Varieties also recorded significant differences for biological yield and the variety M-35-1 recorded significantly higher mean biological yield (11525 kg ha⁻¹) and it was found at par with variety BJV-44. However the lowest mean biological yield was recorded by the variety CSV-29 R (9009 kg ha⁻¹) followed by Phule Suchitra. Biological yield (kg ha⁻¹) was not influenced significantly due to interaction effect of sowing windows and *rabi* sorghum variety.

Harvest index (%)

Harvest index was not influenced significantly due to effect of sowing windows. Among the varieties the harvest index was maximum in Phule Suchitra (27.6 %) and the lowest harvest index recorded with variety M-35-1 (16.71%) which being the characteristic feature of the varieties. There was significant difference among the varieties due to the genetic characters not the treatments. Harvest index (%) was not influenced significantly due to interaction effect of sowing windows and *rabi* sorghum variety.

Conclusion:

Sowing of sorghum at 21st October (42 MW) found to be significantly superior for obtaining higher morpho-physiological traits and yield of sorghum varieties among all the sowing windows. Among the varieties BJV-44 recorded better morpho-physiological traits and and significantly higher seed yield.

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Table: Effect of different sowing windows and varieties on morpho-physiological traits, grain yield, biological yield and harvest index

Treatments	Plant Height (cm) at harvest	No. of functional leaves plant ⁻¹ 90 DAS	Dry matter weight plant ⁻¹ (g) At harvest	No. of days to 50% flowering	No. of days to Phy. maturity	Biological yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	Grain Yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	Harvest Index (%)
Factor A- Sowing windows								
D ₁ - 14 th Oct. (41 MW)	240.77	10.25	216.08	81.17	124.08	10232	2485	24.46
D ₂ - 21 st Oct. (42 MW)	245.46	10.68	217.08	79.67	124.25	10641	2583	24.67
D ₃ -28 th Oct (43 MW)	237.96	10.42	206.78	77.75	121.25	9916	2250	23.19
D ₄ - 4 th Nov (44 MW)	233.25	10.13	198.78	75.08	119.17	9001	2101	23.64
S.E. (m)±	1.24	0.21	0.85	0.50	0.40	123.14	35.93	-
C. D. at 5%	3.60	NS	2.45	1.44	1.17	355.66	103.78	-
Factor B - Varieties								
V ₁ - M 35-1	236.92	10.15	213.38	77.92	120.17	11525	1924	16.71
V ₂ - Phule Suchitra	239.13	10.42	207.96	78.75	122.92	9010	2484	27.61
V ₃ -CSV-29 R	237.55	10.33	205.80	76.83	121.25	9009	2259	25.06
V ₄ - BJV-44	243.83	10.78	211.58	80.17	124.42	10338	2753	26.59
S.E. (m)±	1.24	0.21	0.85	0.50	0.40	123.14	35.93	-
C. D. at 5%	3.60	NS	2.45	1.44	1.17	355.66	103.78	-
Interaction (AXB)								
S.E. (m)±	2.49	0.41	1.70	1.00	0.81	246.28	71.93	-
C. D. at 5%	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	-
GM	239.36	10.40	209.69	78.42	122.19	9970.83	2355.21	-